

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Vigor map generation of the vineyard

SPOKE 6 – Primary Agroindustry

Flagship Project VINO – RM5

DELIVERABLE D5.1

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this document, using remote sensing techniques, we report a summary of maps generation of vineyards of interest. To protect the privacy of the farms involved, outcomes are listed but not visualized. However, we included an example of vigor map of the University of Turin's experimental vineyard generated using our methodology. If interested in having more information on the outcomes generated in the project VINO, please contact the authors of this document.

Maps generation of the vineyard

Field mission for data acquisition

The outcomes of the deliverable have been reached through a series of field missions. These missions encompassed various activities aimed at understanding and enhancing agricultural practices using cutting-edge technologies.

Following a description of the activities carried out for each location and the acquisition data workflow.

Location: Pomaretto (TO)

Activity Description: Field reconnaissance was carried out using both proximal and remote sensing instruments. The main objective was to create digital terrain models (DTMs) to understand the topography and elevation variations of the terrain.

Further field surveys were conducted using proximal and remote sensing tools, focusing on high-slope heroic row vineyard. The last outcome was the development of 2D and 3D vigour maps, aiding in the assessment of the health status of vineyards.

Location: Domodossola (VCO)

Activity Description: Field visits were conducted on experimental plots to test the application of aerial drone-based phytosanitary products. For this purpose, digital terrain models (DTMs) were generated in order to analyse soil elevation variations. This is very useful for this type of application, because it allows the product to be applied smoothly by aerial drone on steep slopes such as those found in heroic viticulture.

Data Acquisition workflow

The data acquisition to create the vigour maps was carried out using UAV with multispectral camera. The flights always took place at noon on sunny days. The aim was to capture images with optimal illumination intensity and minimize shadows in the field of view, which resulted to be

almost null. The UAV path planning was performed in order to guarantee an overlapping rate between adjacent images greater than 80% for the forward overlapping and greater than 70 for the lateral one, in accordance with the good practices described in literature.

The sensor adopted to acquire multispectral imagery was an Altum-PT (2. AgEagle Aerial Systems Inc.) multispectral camera, which features 5 sensors with 3.2 Megapixel resolution with the following spectral resolution coverage:

- Blue (475 nm center, 32 nm bandwidth)
- Green (560 nm center, 27 nm bandwidth)
- Red (668 nm center, 14 nm bandwidth)
- Red edge (717 nm center, 12 nm bandwidth)
- Near-IR (842 nm center, 57 nm bandwidth) of 37 nm.

The camera has been equipped on a DJI Matrice 300 quadcopter, with a support that allow a nadiral view of the sensor. The 5 shutters of the camera were set to open simultaneously, so that the multiband measurements resulted to be synchronous. Acquired data were corrected in relation to light changes during the flight by using reflectance panel and exploiting information provided by a Downwelling Light Sensor (DLS2), an advanced incident light sensor that measures the ambient light and sun angle for each of the five multispectral bands of the camera.

Finally, a georeferenced ortho-mosaics of the vineyard was generated by processing aerial images with Agisoft Metashape (Agisoft LLC) software, which performs photogrammetric procedure to generate a GeoTIFF file in the WGS84 EPSG:4326 reference system. The accuracy of the georeferencing task was ensured by placing six markers as ground control points (GCP), and their positions were acquired using the Stonex S900A differential GNSS with an accuracy of about 2 cm.

By processing the multispectral orthophotos, vigour maps were created with vegetative indices (e.g. NDVI or NDRE) using the following algorithms:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED}$$

$$NDRE = \frac{NIR - RED\ EDGE}{NIR + RED\ EDGE}$$

Vigour map generation

The outcomes of this deliverable are therefore orthophotos in tif format representing the elevation of the terrain (Digital Terrain Map), or orthophotos in RGB colours, or multispectral orthophotos or vineyard vigour maps, or multispectral 3D point cloud.

With the raw multispectral orthophotos it is possible to calculate vigour indices, with multispectral 3D point cloud it is possible to assess the vigour of the lateral canopy in addition to the top canopy represented in the orthophotos.

Below is a table 1 describing the outcomes of this deliverable.

Table 1. Description of outcomes

File name	Description
20231025_Pomaretto_01_3Dcloud_multispectral.txt	Multispectral 3D point cloud
20231025_Pomaretto_01_dtm	Digital terrain map
20231025_Pomaretto_01_multispectral.tif	Raw multispectral orthophoto
20231025_Pomaretto_01_NDVI.tif	Vigour map NDVI Orthophoto
20231025_Pomaretto_02_multispectral.tif	Raw multispectral orthophoto
20231025_Pomaretto_02_NDRE.tif	Vigour map NDRE Orthophoto
20231025_Pomaretto_023Dcloud_multispectral.txt	Multispectral 3D point cloud
20240229_domodossola_filare_dtm.tif	Digital terrain map
20240229_domodossola_filare_ortofoto.tif	RGB Orthophoto
20240229_domodossola_pergola_DTM.tif	Digital terrain map
20240229_domodossola_pergola_Ortofoto.tif	RGB Orthophoto

Outcomes have been delivered to the Spoke

Examples of maps

In the following, examples of all the maps generation using the methodology outlined above. The location is of the University of Turin's experimental vineyard.

Figure 1 - 2D RGB ortomosaic

Figure 2- 3D RGB dense cloud points

Figure 3 - 3D RGB dense cloud points with ground control point details

Figure 4 - Digital terrain map (DTM)

Figure 5 - Vigour map